

FORMATION OF RESEARCH COMPETENCIES IN STUDENTS THROUGH THE PROCESS OF SOLVING NON-STANDARD PROBLEMS IN PHYSICS

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***Abstract.** This article discusses the formation of readiness of future physics teachers for research activities and research competencies through solving non-standard problems in physics. It highlights issues related to improving the quality of education by using research work.*

***Keywords:** formation, readiness for research activities, component, physics.*

Introduction

The pace of modern social progress and emerging challenges concerning quality and efficiency in various spheres of human activity largely depend on how capable our society is today in applying a research-based approach to solving intellectual and practical problems. This approach is reflected in the reform of the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which emphasizes the need to modernize the content of general education and stresses that the main outcomes of teaching and upbringing should be the set of core competencies of students in intellectual, creative, research, and other activity areas. The achievement of these outcomes requires strengthening personality-oriented education.

According to the current State Standard of Higher Education, students studying physics must acquire skills to conduct observations, plan and perform analysis and synthesis, formulate hypotheses, and build mathematical models for word problems. Students should develop cognitive interests and competencies through solving physics problems and independently acquiring new knowledge.

Methodology

Based on the above, the relevance of the problem of forming research competencies in students is beyond doubt. The issue of improving the quality and effectiveness of professional training of specialists can be addressed by implementing innovative technologies in the educational process of higher education institutions. This, in turn, fundamentally raises the quality of educational services and ensures the training of future specialists equipped with mobile knowledge, flexible professional methods, and critical thinking.

Scientific research work of students (SRWS) is an integral part of the educational process, as it represents one of the proven methods for identifying talented and capable students and preparing them for independent creative scientific research activities.

A statement attributed to E. Fermi, which is likely agreed upon by every professional physicist, is: “To know physics means to be able to solve problems.” In other words, the level of preparation in physics is determined by the level of difficulty of the problems that a student can solve. A non-standard physics problem is one that differs from classical problems by several parameters: the presence or absence of additional information, the formulation of the problem’s conditions, or the method of its solution.

A non-standard physics problem is designed to develop in students the general skills necessary for solving any problem. In such problems, students learn to identify the conditions and requirements of the problem and select the data necessary for its solution. Solving these problems develops cognitive skills such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, etc., and also allows students to demonstrate their creative abilities, goal orientation, and the ability to develop a preliminary framework of activities to solve the problem.

For more convenient use of non-standard problems in the educational process, we have developed the following classification of non-standard physics problems (Table 1).

Table 1

Classification of Non-Standard Problems

Types of Non-Standard Problems	By content	With Technical Content
		With Natural Science Content
		With Historical Content
	By form	Drawing Problems
		Creative Problems
		Paradox Problems
		Experimental problems

Non-standard problems with technical content are problems that help students become acquainted with the principles and construction of mechanisms and machines, the transmission and conversion of energy, technologies of industrial and agricultural production, control systems, and the ability to apply physics knowledge to explain the operation of technical objects.

Problems with natural science content are physics problems that include elements of biology, geography, ecology, and biophysics. These problems can be used by teachers during lessons and extracurricular activities, as well as by students themselves for lesson preparation, extracurricular events, self-development, and to foster creativity and general knowledge. This type of problem teaches functional literacy that is, the ability to find solutions in complex situations based on real-life circumstances [Semke A.I.].

Problems with historical content involve the use of historical material, both general history and specific elements of the history of physics.

Drawing problems are a type of physics problem where the condition is given in the form of graphs, drawings, illustrations, etc. [Shmarova T.S.].

Creative problems occupy one of the most important places in physics education. The feature of this type of problem is the absence of a clear algorithm or strict sequence of actions for solving the problems. Using creative problems in physics education helps students develop ingenuity and resourcefulness and fosters creative thinking.

Results and discussion

Creative problems are subdivided into discovery problems and invention problems. Applying these generalized types to physics, one can conditionally distinguish between "research problems" and "design problems." In research-type problems, an external description of a phenomenon is usually given, and the student is asked to explain the causes and regularities of this phenomenon.

Design-type problems have a practical orientation and propose that students create, build, or measure something; therefore, these problems primarily answer the question "How to do it?" A paradox is a statement that may seem contradictory or impossible, yet may turn out to be true.

Paradoxes are most often created using two statements, one of which is false and the other true [Kazakov A.N.]. A physical paradox is a contradiction in the description of physical processes.

Experimental problems contribute to the development of thinking and cognitive activity, facilitate a deeper understanding of the essence of phenomena, and develop the skill of formulating hypotheses and testing them in practice. Within the framework of SRWS (Scientific Research Work of Students), students become familiar with the main methods of work in their specialty and with the methodology of scientific research work in general. SRWS helps create the prerequisites for future active participation of graduates in the process of implementing scientific and pedagogical social progress into production practice.

At the Department of Physics Teaching Methodology of the Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz, a certain experience has been developed in forming students' readiness for scientific research work. The involvement of students in investigating problems in the field of education and upbringing takes place in connection with the study of core courses such as "Methods of Teaching Physics," "Methods of Teaching Astronomy," "Methods of Solving Physics Problems," and others.

We strive to identify capable students starting from the first year through passive educational work, conducting conversations and discussions with them on various issues related to the methodology of teaching physics. In the second and third years, when pedagogical cycle courses begin, the department's lecturers face the task of developing students' readiness for pedagogical education. It is important that students not only become aware of the diversity of pedagogical knowledge sources but also thoroughly understand the specificity of each.

Some students become so passionate about educational issues that they deepen their knowledge through further independent study. An important factor here is the active cooperation between students and department lecturers in solving pedagogical problems, which contributes to the formation of a new attitude toward pedagogical science. Such systematic and planned work fosters students' desires and interest in scientific research activities.

Completing individual assignments in the course "Methods of Teaching Physics," presentations, essays, note-taking, and other student work with pedagogical literature provides an opportunity to develop their ability to extract necessary information from various sources, use it competently in reports and presentations, skillfully make references, group, organize, and systematize the obtained data. Such work prepares students for the process of self-educational activity. The system of general pedagogical training for students cannot be realized without a sufficiently high level of student readiness for pedagogical self-education [Karlybaeva G.].

Conclusion

By summarizing it should be suggested that self-education is considered a social category and the core, the backbone of continuous education. Already in the fourth year, during their teaching practice, students apply theoretical knowledge in new conditions to solve specific practical problems. Only through the practical application of knowledge can students firmly master skills and abilities and use them in various conditions and pedagogical situations. It is on this basis that the creative thinking of future physics teachers develops, forming a creative approach to pedagogical activity.

A distinctive feature in organizing the process of pedagogical practice is the variability of technologies that activate the mental activity of the interns: these include problem-based questions, heuristic discussions, role-playing games all methods, techniques, and approaches where the key and important component is the qualitative level of self-education of the future physics teacher.

Knowledge of the structure and essence of readiness for Scientific Research Work of Students (SRWS) allowed us to develop a strategy for instructors to correctly organize and direct the students' academic work to achieve the optimal result — the formation of a high level of readiness for scientific research activities in the vast majority of students.

SRWS is given as an important place at the department. It is an effective means of improving the qualifications of future teachers, enhancing their theoretical and practical knowledge, and simultaneously satisfying the desire of young people to acquire knowledge in various fields of science. SRWS is an important form of nurturing talented students.

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